

Antennal evolution in the Brachycera (Diptera), with a reassessment of terminology relating to the flagellum

[Die Evolution der Antennen bei den Brachycera (Diptera), nebst einer
Neubewertung der zum Flagellum gehörenden Terminologie]

by

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Abstract

The primitive brachycerous antenna comprises scape, pedicel and eight segments in a terminal series called the flagellum. Transformation to the aristate cyclorrhaphous form was considered by authors to have been exemplified by transformations in Stratiomyidae. Discussions of evolutionary changes focused mainly on numbers of flagellomeres, which were considered to have little phylogenetic significance because of homoplasy. An alternative antennal transformation series in Vermileonidae is described, and is proposed as a paradigm of antennal evolution in Brachycera. It is hypothesised that the brachycerous antenna evolved towards assortment of the sensory functions of mechanoreception and chemoreception. At an early stage an apical mechanoreceptor evolved from segments 9 and 10, resulting in permanent retention of these segments. Through progressive fusion of segments, an enlarged flagellar base evolved as a specialised carrier of chemoreceptors. These developments constitute a synapomorphy of the Brachycera. A revised terminology is proposed for components of the brachycerous antenna. To avoid inconsistency, it is suggested that the term '**flagellum**' in descriptive writing be restricted to the **Nematocera**; in **Brachycera**, the term '**postpedicel**' is adopted for the flagellar base, and the term '**stylus**' is recommended strictly for the mechanoreceptor distal to the postpedicel; the term '**arista**' should be restricted to the distinctive mechanoreceptor of the Cyclorrhapha. It is suggested that the emergence of the Brachycera from nematocerous ancestors involved coevolution of antennal transformation and pseudotracheate labella, linked to a new feeding mode appropriate in new floras that appeared in the Triassic and Jurassic.

Key words

brachycera, antennae, synapomorphy, mechanoreceptors, chemoreceptors, terminology, postpedicel, pseudotracheae, mesozoic floras

Zusammenfassung

Die Antenne der Brachycera besteht im Grundplan aus Scapus (Fühlerglied 1), Pedicellus (2) und einem distalen Komplex aus acht Segmenten (3–10), der entsprechend seiner Homologie bisher als Flagellum oder Fühlergeißel bezeichnet wurde. Vorstellungen zur Evolution der Antenna der Cyclorrhapha, mit drei proximalen Gliedern und einer distalen Arista, stützten sich auf den Vergleich mit Abwandlungen des Antennenbaus innerhalb der Stratiomyiden. Im Mittelpunkt der Diskussion stand die Anzahl der Flagellomeren, der wegen konvergenter Entwicklungen nur wenig Aussagekraft zur Phylogenese beigemessen wurde. Eine Transformationsreihe bei den Vermileoniden wird beschrieben und als Alternativmodell für die Evolution der Antennen bei den Brachyceren präsentiert. Nach dieser Vorstellung differenzierte die Fühlergeißel sich in zwei Abschnitte mit verschiedener Sinnesfunktion. Die Segmente 9 und 10 entwickelten sich frühzeitig zu einem apikalen Mechanorezeptor und blieben mit dieser Funktion dauerhaft erhalten. An der Basis des Flagellum entstand durch fortschreitende Verschmelzung von Segmenten ein größeres Glied (Postpedicellus), auf dem sich die chemischen Sinnesorgane konzentrieren. Diese Entwicklungstendenzen bilden eine Synapomorphie der Brachycera. Für deskriptive Zwecke wird vorgeschlagen, den Begriff **Flagellum** nur bei **Nematoceren** zu gebrauchen und für **Brachyceren** stattdessen die Termini **Postpedicellus** und **Stylus** (Griffel) oder **Arista** zu verwenden. Die Umgestaltung der Antennen und die gleichzeitige Differenzierung von Pseudotracheen auf den Labellen werden als Schlüsselereignisse in der Entwicklung der Brachyceren aus mückenartigen Vorfahren gewertet und mit der Erschließung neuer pflanzlicher Nahrungsquellen in Trias und Jura erklärt.

Stichwörter

Brachycera, Antennen, Synapomorphie, mechanische und chemische Sinnesorgane, Terminologie, Postpedicellus, Pseudotracheen, Flora, Mesozoikum

Introduction

It is generally accepted that the plesiomorphic form of antenna in the Brachycera has 10 segments; these are the scape, the pedicel, and eight segments that constitute the flagellum (HENNIG 1967, 1971, 1972, 1973; McALPINE 1989; WOODLEY 1989). The flagellomeres are clearly separated from each other, and together they form a gradually tapering unit commonly called a stylus. This plesiomorphic form is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Plesiomorphic brachycerous antenna; the segments are numbered, and the traditional terminology of components is indicated.

The most derived form of the antenna in the Brachycera is considered to be that which occurs throughout the Cyclorrhapha (Fig. 19). In this form, the scape and pedicel are followed by the basal member of the flagellum, which typically is ventrally enlarged to the extent that it is the largest and most conspicuous component of the antenna. Placed anterodorsally is a porrect, slender structure named the arista, which is composed of three segments – two very small basal segments, and an elongate, acuminate, apical one.

It has been assumed that this highly apomorphic antenna was derived from the plesiomorphic form, but there is no satisfactory account in the literature as to the sequences of morphological changes that could have occurred. The few authors who have examined antennal forms in the Brachycera have been concerned mainly with the variable numbers of flagellomeres and the significance of these numbers for classification. Little understanding has been achieved about the homology of components of the antenna in the higher flies. The factors that might have driven antennal evolution – the functional basis for change – seem to have been neglected. What, for example, was the manner of segment loss? – and in what sequence did this occur? Why is the basal member of the flagellum enlarged? – and why should the terminal elements of the flagellum be attenuated?

The prospect of arriving at answers to such questions has been diverted by a commonly held view that the loss of flagellomeres occurred frequently and independently in numerous lineages within the Brachycera – even within individual families. GRIFFITHS (1994), for example, considered the condition “at most 4 flagellomeres present” to be apomorphic relative to “8 flagellomeres present”, but that such a reduction “... is obviously subject to homoplasy in the Brachycera.” McALPINE (1989) similarly stated that reductions in the number of flagellomeres from the plesiomorphic 8-segmented condition “... have occurred independently and in dif-

ferent manners". If the discussion is confined to segment numbers, then homoplasy will always be invoked and the nature of differences in antennal form will escape understanding. In examinations of antennal transformation in the pioneering papers by HENNIG (1967, 1971, 1972, 1973), and in the broad overviews by McALPINE (1989) and WOODLEY (1989), the view was expressed that antennal forms in the Stratiomyidae, as described and figured by JORGENSEN & JAMES (1968), represent the transition assumed to have occurred between the filiform antennal type in Nematocera and the aristate type in Cyclorrhapha. McALPINE in particular, in discussing flagellar form in the Brachycera, considered that the antennae of some Stratiomyidae, especially in Pachygasterinae and Sarginae, illustrate the kind of transition that occurred generally in the Brachycera. His conclusions accorded with his view that the Stratiomyidae are a key group with possible affinities to the Cyclorrhapha. The excellent figures provided by JORGENSEN & JAMES (1968) show, however, that flagellar diversification in Stratiomyidae is complex, involving multiple autapomorphic trends spread through different clades. Some of the antennal forms have no equivalents elsewhere in the Brachycera. A more parsimonious argument, for a more direct course of evolutionary change, can be derived from an informative transformation series that occurs in Vermileonidae.

Antennal transformation in Vermileonidae

During the course of studies directed at a revised taxonomy of the Afrotropical Vermileonidae, it became apparent that a transformation series exists which clarifies the nature and direction of flagellar evolution (STUCKENBERG 1996, 1998). This series is illustrated in Figs 2–9.

- Fig. 2** The plesiomorphic form with eight flagellomeres forming a tapering unit; the apical flagellomere (flagellomere 8, segment 10) is elongate subconical, and the basal one (flagellomere 1, segment 3) is much longer than the others; chemoreceptor sensilla and tactile sensilla chaetica occur on all flagellomeres. This form occurs in a few species of *Vermipardus* STUCKENBERG, which is the Afrotropical genus with the most plesiomorphic condition of the male genitalia and mouthparts (STUCKENBERG 1995); the same primitive flagellum occurs in all known species of *Vermilyn*x STUCKENBERG (see, for example, STUCKENBERG 1996, Fig. 9).
- Fig. 3** The apical flagellomere (segment 10) has become more elongate and slender, and now has only a tactile function as the chemoreceptor sensilla have become lost; this condition, with the relative length of the apical flagellomere differing between species, occurs in the other species of *Vermipardus* (as illustrated by STUCKENBERG 1995, 1997).
- Fig. 4** The apical flagellomere (segment 10) is now very slender and elongate; some preceding flagellomeres, particularly the penultimate one, are narrowed, and some flagellomeres distal to the basal one are shortened; both apical and penultimate flagellomeres now lack chemoreceptor sensilla, and have only sensilla chaetica. Such a condition is characteristic of the species of *Leptynoma* WESTWOOD, subgenus *Perianthomyia* STUCKENBERG (see STUCKENBERG 1996, Fig. 2).
- Fig. 5** First stage of flagellar compaction, with fusion of flagellomeres 1 and 2 (segments 3 and 4); this occurs in some species of *Leptynoma* WESTWOOD s. str. (see STUCKENBERG 1996, Fig. 3).

- Fig. 6** Progressive distal fusion of flagellomeres with flagellar base; in *Leptynoma* (*L. appendiculata*) (BEZZI, 1926) (Fig. 6), flagellomere 3 (segment 5) is extensively fused with completely fused flagellomeres 1 + 2 (segments 3 + 4). In *Lampromyia pilosula* ENGEL, 1929 (Fig. 7), flagellomere 4 (segment 6) is largely fused with the compound flagellar base consisting of flagellomeres 1 + 2 + 3 (segments 3 + 4 + 5).
- Fig. 7**
- Fig. 8** Complete fusion of flagellomeres 1–5 (segments 3–7); the example shown is *Lampromyia hemmingseni* STUCKENBERG, 1971; the same condition occurs in *Lampromyia canariensis* Macquart, 1839 (STUCKENBERG 1998, Fig. 1).
- Fig. 9** Complete fusion of flagellomeres 1–6 (segments 3–8) into a large flagellar base, leaving free only the small penultimate flagellomere 7 (segment 9) and an elongate, slender apical flagellomere 8 (segment 10). This occurs in other species of *Lampromyia* MACQUART – the example illustrated is *L. flavida* ENGEL & CUTHBERTSON, 1937 – see also *L. iberica* STUCKENBERG, 1998, *L. funebris* DUFOUR, 1850, *L. cylindrica* (FABRICIUS, 1794), and *L. pallida* MACQUART, 1835, illustrated in STUCKENBERG (1998, Figs 4, 5, 6 and 8 respectively).

The manner of loss of flagellomeres is evident from conditions seen in several species: flagellomeres have disappeared one by one through progressive fusion with the enlarged basal member of the flagellum. There is no example of incipient loss of a flagellomere as a result of reduction. Several cases of incompletely fused segments are known; the flagellum in Fig. 6 shows partial fusion between the basal member and segment 5 (flagellomere 3); in Fig. 7 there is incomplete fusion between segment 6 (flagellomere 4) and the basal member. Incomplete fusion is similarly shown in the flagellum of *Lampromyia fortunata* STUCKENBERG, 1971, and *L. lecerfi* SÉGUY, 1928 (STUCKENBERG 1998, Figs 2 and 7 respectively). Such partial fusion is best detected through examination of cleared, slide-mounted antennae; an intersegmental suture between flagellomeres may be present on the outer surface but does not continue onto the inner surface. The process of fusion may also be intraspecifically variable; for example, the holotype and a paratype of *Lampromyia rebecca* STUCKENBERG, 1996 differ in that the holotype has only two flagellomeres free distal to the large basal member of the flagellum, and the paratype has three (STUCKENBERG 1996).

The end result of this transformation in Vermileonidae was the evolution of a slender, two-segmented, terminal mechanoreceptor, borne distally on a greatly enlarged compound flagellar base evidently formed by the progressive fusion of segments 3–8. Throughout this transformation, segments 10 and 9 were never lost. This was because segment 10, as the apical component of the antenna most likely to interact with the physical environment, always had a special sensory role. In the most plesiomorphic antenna (Fig. 2), it shared both a tactile and a chemosensory role with the other flagellomeres, but with the loss of chemoreceptor sensilla at an early stage (Fig. 3), segment 10 was committed exclusively to a mechanoreceptor role. Also at an early stage (Fig. 4), segment 9 (the penultimate flagellomere) became coadapted through loss of chemoreceptor function and rapid adaptation of form to be the basal element of an attenuated, two-segmented mechanoreceptor. It is hypothesised that comparable evolu-

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Figs 2-9: Antennal transformation in Vermileonidae. In all cases, the basal element of the flagellum (postpedicel) is shaded; this comprises only segment 3 in Figs 2-4. In Figs 5-9, flagellar segments fuse progressively into a composite postpedicel; finally, in Fig. 9 only segments 9 and 10 are unfused and together form an apical mechanoreceptor. Incompletely fused segments are considered to be part of the postpedicel.

2

Vemipardus
(some spp.)

3

Vemipardus
(other spp.)

4

Leptynomia (*Peri-*
anthomyia) spp.

5

Leptynomia s. str.
(some spp.)

6

Leptynomia (s. str.)
appendiculata (BEZZI)

7

Lampromyia
pilosula ENGEL

8

Lampromyia
hemmingseni
STUCKENBERG

9

Lampromyia
flavida ENGEL &
CUTHBERTSON

tion of such an apical mechanoreceptor, through early modification of segments 9 + 10, occurred throughout the Brachycera. Even if flagellar segments are interpreted as having been lost by reduction instead of fusion, the morphological identity of the terminal flagellomere as segment 10 remains valid.

The identity of flagellar segments in brachyceran flies would thus be more correctly determined if counting of segments is done backwards, starting with the apical segment as number 10. Through counting of unfused segments, the number of fused segments making up the compound flagellar base can be estimated. Antennal segmentation can then be expressed by a numerical formula in the following form (relating, for example, to Fig. 8): 1 + 2 + 3–7 + 8 + 9 + 10. Counting from the scape forwards could lead to false conclusions that apical segments were lost in flies with fewer than ten antennal segments.

Antennal forms in Nemestrinoidea, Asiloidea and Eremoneura suggest that a similar transformation sequence occurred in these lineages. In some Nemestrinoidea and Asiloidea, additional adaptations involving reduction in size and further fusion affected the form of the terminal segment (HENNIG 1972, McALPINE 1989).

Antennal structure as a synapomorphy

Such a transformation series is proposed as a paradigm of antennal evolution in the Brachycera. It resulted in differentiation of the primitive flagellum into two completely dissimilar but complementary sensory systems, characteristic of the Brachycera. These are:

The apical mechanoreceptor. This has been known as an arista or a stylus, depending arbitrarily on the degree of fusion and attenuation attained. Only in a few small homoeodactylous families – Xylophagidae, Xylomyidae, Pelecorhynchidae – do all genera retain the primitive flagellum in which mechanoreceptor and chemoreceptor functions are incompletely assorted. There is a pervasive trend towards compaction, reduction of segmentation, and apical attenuation. When the mechanoreceptor is slender, the penultimate flagellomere is commonly very short; it may have a flexing role, or possibly its function is to register degrees of stress or movement in the terminal segment when this is in physical contact with an object.

The exceptional structural modifications found in the stylus throughout the Asilomorpha were investigated by HENNIG (1972). This two-segmented stylus is unusual for being relatively much reduced in size (as in Fig. 13), and for having a distinctive, non-pubescent, hyaline terminal segment; moreover, the stylus may not be apical, but offset preapically in a depression situated laterally or dorsally on the basal flagellar member (as in Scenopinidae). This apomorphic condition suggests another sensory role for the stylus, but what this could be is unknown. It may be significant in this regard, that the asilomorph families (Therevidae, Scenopinidae, Asilidae, Mydidae, Apioceridae, Bombyliidae) have a high proportion of members that are terrestrial, among which are many exceptionally large flies.

The compound flagellar base. Formed by progressive fusion of the third segment with succeeding distal segments, in its most derived forms it probably comprises fused segments 3–7 or 3–8. This structure is specialised in different degrees as a carrier of olfactory chemoreceptors. Enlargement of its surface area by the amalgamation of segments, and through various subsequent changes of form, was associated with the following developments:

- ▶ an increase in the number of chemoreceptor sensilla and their concentration in certain areas, thereby enhancing sensitivity thresholds as these are determined by the number of sensilla (CHAPMAN 1982);

- evolution of a greater diversity of chemoreceptors, thereby favouring a wider spectrum of chemical sensitivity;
- evolution of invaginated sensory pits, in which certain specialised chemoreceptors are concentrated;
- forward-facing orientation of sensilla, appropriate for more efficient location of food, mates and breeding resources.

Flagellar evolution was thus associated primarily with separation of the sensory functions of olfaction and mechanoreception. It followed a consistent course of significant anagenetic reorganisation, resulting in new flagellar structures equivalent throughout the Brachycera. The flagellar base evolved to be the main centre for olfactory sensing; contact chemoreception by gustatory sensilla on the proboscis and tarsi probably evolved in parallel.

In all the brachyceran lineages loosely grouped as the Heterodactyla (Nemestrinoidea + Asiloidea + Eremoneura), no example of the 10-segmented plesiomorphic antenna (as in Fig. 1) has been preserved. Flagellar modification has been pervasive, and no more than the terminal three flagellomeres are still preserved (1 + 2 + 3–7 + 8 + 9 + 10) in some Nemestrinidae and in Cyclorrhapha. A two-segmented stylus is basic in Empidoidea and Asiloidea. It therefore has to be assumed that the plesiomorphic form of antenna (Fig. 1, or something similar) was the precursor of the stages of flagellar differentiation preserved in modern Heterodactyla. Fossils known up to the present shed no light on this; by the Upper Jurassic, extinct families such as the Eremochaetidae and Archisargidae (NAGATOMI & YANG 1998), and the extant Nemestrinidae and Empididae (REN 1998a), already had an aristate antenna. This assumption is reasonable, as the monophyly of all Brachycera is demonstrated by other synapomorphies, and it is more parsimonious to argue that a single anagenetic transformation occurred, than to postulate convergence by a variety of unknown evolutionary routes.

The proposal that flagellar evolution in Brachycera was associated with fusion and sensory functions is not new. HENNIG (1973) observed as follows: "Da bei den Brachycera die allgemeine Entwicklung zu einer scharfen Trennung zwischen dem Grundglied der Fühlergeißel (Postpedicellus, Funiculus) und der aus den übrigen, mehr oder weniger reduzierten, Geißelgliedern gebildeten Arista führt ist es höchst bedauerlich, daß die Frage, wie die Verteilung der Sinnesorgane durch diese Entwicklung beeinflusst wird, bisher überhaupt noch nicht untersucht wurde." McALPINE (1989) considered it probable that the basal component of the flagellum is a composite structure. He reasoned that it could be composed of at least three or four flagellomeres, since this seemed to be indicated by the distribution of "microscopic sensory pits" in stratiomyid antennae illustrated by JORGENSEN & JAMES (1968). He conjectured that "... the arrangement of sensory pits and other microstructures in the first flagellomere of certain members of the Asilomorpha and Muscomorpha reflect the original segmentation involved." He noted, however, that "... insufficient comparative data are available to resolve this problem."

This differentiation of the flagellum into two sensory structures is a significant synapomorphy of the Brachycera. Previously, HENNIG (1967, 1973) considered that reduction of the number of flagellomeres from 14 (in the groundplan of the order Diptera) to eight, to be a synapomorphy of the Brachycera. This was accepted by WOODLEY (1989), McALPINE (1989), SINCLAIR et al. (1993), and GRIFFITHS (1994). Reduction of flagellomeres to eight could, however, be a weak character; nematocerous ancestors of the Brachycera might also have had eight segments, in which case it would be a synapomorphy of a clade larger than the Brachycera.

That such a situation could have existed is suggested by the oldest fossil currently assigned to the Brachycera: *Alinka cara* KRZEMIŃSKI, 1992 of the Upper Triassic. It has eight flagellar segments, but this is inconclusive; the flagellomeres are submoniliform, a condition found in various Nematocera but not in Brachycera. Moreover, the wing venation is close to that of the fossil nematocerous family Procrampptomomyiidae, so *Alinka* could have been a nematoceran.

Flagellar terminology

This topic needs to be addressed because of the widespread confusion and inconsistency in the literature, mostly unnoticed, regarding the names applied to antennal parts of the Brachycera.

The compound flagellar base clearly requires a name. In the case of the plesiomorphic antenna with eight flagellomeres, the basal one is correctly called segment 3, and has often been called the first flagellomere. When segments have fused and collectively form an enlarged basal element in the flagellum, this is a new structure, so it is misleading and morphologically incorrect to call it a flagellomere. HENNIG (1967, 1971, 1972, 1973), not taking the fusion of segments into account, called the flagellar base a 'postpedicel' or 'funiculus'. As defined in TORRE-BUENO (1989), a funiculus (or funicle) is "... that part of the flagellum of the antenna proximal to the club ... in insects with geniculate antennae, eg. Curculionidae ... and ants." Diptera lack geniculate antennae, so by this definition cannot be said to have a funiculus.

The term 'stylus' has always been rather imprecise; it has been applied inconsistently, sometimes to all of the flagellum regardless of modified segmentation, at other times only to the segments distal to the flagellar base, and even to the terminal segment alone. It was used particularly when free flagellomeres making up the mechanoreceptor lacked the attenuation characteristic of an arista. The term has had a long history, but now requires redefinition.

The dipterous 'flagellum' has been defined, like the scape and pedicel, usually only in terms of its position in a series of antennal components: "... the third part of the antenna beyond the pedicel" (TORRE-BUENO 1989). The original meaning of the word (diminutive of 'flagrum', L., a whip or lash) gives it appropriateness in Nematocera, in which the usually elongate flagellum consists of segments which are close copies of one another, and make up an extended, smoothly and only gradually tapering whole which is functionally a single structure. In Brachycera, the term has been applied not just to a discrete sequence of segments, but collectively to two structural components with different forms and functions, and with diverging morphological histories. These two structures in a morphological sense together still make up the flagellum, but use of this term in the Brachycera has contributed to the confusion and inconsistency in the naming of antennal components. Because of this, and the divergent nature of the flagellum in the two suborders, clarity and consistency in descriptive and taxonomic writing could be achieved if the term 'flagellum' is restricted to the Nematocera. The nematocerous antenna thus would comprise the standard components of **scape + pedicel + flagellum**.

The term 'postpedicel' is seldom used; it is not entirely felicitous as the prefix 'post-' in morphology has the primary meaning of "behind" or "after", and the postpedicel is anterior to the pedicel. There is no other name; rather than coining a new one, I suggest that it be retained in the sense that HENNIG used it: namely, for the enlarged flagellar base immediately distal to the pedicel (definitions are offered below). It is further suggested that the term 'stylus' be applied strictly to the mechanoreceptor distal to the postpedicel. Thus, the following four-part revised terminology of antennal components in Brachycera is proposed: **scape + pedicel + postpedicel + stylus**.

MCALPINE (1989) considered that the three-segmented condition of the terminal mechanoreceptor of Cyclorrhapha is an autapomorphy. This is surely correct; the structure is distinctive, but not only for its triple segmentation; it also has a suite of derived conditions: the extreme attenuation with relative stiffness of the apical segment – diverse specialisations of the apical segment through development of pubescence, fine hair-like vestiture, or delicate branching on dorsal and ventral surfaces – and the small bisegmented basal element which evidently provides flexibility or may register stress when the apical segment is put under pressure. This is a uniquely apomorphic stylus, for which a name is warranted. It is proposed that the term *arista* be reserved for the cyclorrhaphous antennal mechanoreceptor. By doing this, morphological inconsistencies can be avoided – like, for example, the labelling of a two-segmented stylus of slender but different form as an arista, on the antennae of a stratiomyid and a dolichopodid in Volume 1 of the 'Manual of Nearctic Diptera' (Figs 2.24 and 2.34 respectively). The cyclorrhaphous antenna (Figs 15, 19) thus comprises **scape + pedicel + postpedicel + arista**.

The following definitions of antennal components are proposed:

- scape:** segment 1, articulating on the head capsule;
- pedicel:** segment 2, distal to and next after the scape;
- flagellum:** in the morphological sense, all segments collectively that are distal to the pedicel; in the structural sense, the organ (or organs) constituted by these segments, recommended for use in Nematocera only;
- postpedicel:** situated distal to the pedicel in Brachycera; either the third antennal segment alone when 10 segments are present (in such cases, usually both longer and thicker than succeeding segments), or a compound structure formed by sequential distal fusion of the third segment with successive distal segments;
- stylus:** the structure consisting of any free segments distal to the postpedicel, hypothesised to terminate apically in segment 10; used preferentially for the orthorrhaphous Brachycera;
- arista:** the three-segmented structure distal to the postpedicel of Cyclorrhapha; it is a highly specialised stylus, comprising an elongate, very slender, usually acuminate terminal segment which is hypothesised to be segment 10, articulating on a small basal element apparently composed of much reduced segments 9 + 8.

Some factors affecting postpedicel form

Given that the role of olfactory chemoreception varies in relation to the main features of adult lifestyle of a brachyceran fly, it can be expected that the form of the postpedicel will vary (Figs 10–15). This is clearly demonstrated, for example, in taxa that include both haematophagous and autogenous clades. The need to locate hosts for bloodmeals by female Tabanidae has produced changes in the postpedicel characteristic of this family. The postpedicel is enlarged posterodorsally into a projecting extension that takes various forms, thereby increasing surface area to accommodate a special field of forward-facing chemoreceptors (Fig. 16). A linked adaptation in Tabanidae is the enlarged and curved apical palpal segment, which provides for an increase of chemoreceptors concentrated in a strip (often in a shallow groove) along the dorsal surface. Autogenous female tabanids lacking fully-formed mandibles do not require such specialised fields of chemoreceptors, so commonly have a secondarily reduced postpedicel; the palps are also reduced and less curved.

A comparable suite of adaptations occurs in Athericidae. The haematophagous genera have the postpedicel enlarged below, under the level of attachment of the stylus, to form a surface densely covered with anteriorly-directed chemoreceptors (Fig. 17). Autogenous taxa have a much reduced postpedicel (Fig. 18); palpal form reflects these contrasting lifestyles, as in Tabanidae. A similar postpedicel enlargement and sensory specialisation occurs in those species of the rhagionid genus *Symphoromyia* FRAUENFELD which are bloodsuckers. Such antennal forms suggest a way of determining which fossil species may have been haematophagous.

Figs 10–15: Brachycerous antennae, showing various forms of the postpedicel (shaded), and different forms of the stylus distal to the postpedicel. – 10: *Arthropeas* spec. (Xylophagidae); – 11: *Bolbomyia* spec. (Rhagionidae); – 12: *Breviperna* spec. (Therevidae); – 13: *Henicomomyia* spec. (Therevidae); – 14: *Anthalia* spec. (Empididae); – 15: *Lauxaniella* spec. (Lauxaniidae). Based on figures of McALPINE et al. (1981).

Fig. 16: Antenna of female *Tabanus sudeticus* ZELLER, 1842, with postpedicel shaded, showing the dorsobasal enlargement of the postpedicel accomodating a field of chemoreceptors (see text).

Adaptation of the postpedicel for its chemoreceptor role through enlargement of its surface has produced an almost standard modification in the Schizophora (Fig. 19). This allowed for multiplication and diversification of sensilla, and invagination of the surface into sensory pits, relating to features of life-history such as anthophily, nectarivory, saprophagy and coprophagy. This enlargement affected the lower part of the postpedicel, causing it to acquire ventrally projecting, pendulous, oval, reniform, pyriform or rounded shapes, with the arista commonly situated dorsally, anterodorsally or preapically.

On becoming brachycerous

Present information from the rapidly expanding field of palaeoentomology shows that diversification of the Brachycera was underway during the Jurassic. Although the Upper Triassic fly *Alinka cara* KRZEMIŃSKI (1992) was described as the earliest known brachyceran, this species may in fact be nematocerous (see above). According to the summary by NAGATOMI & YANG (1998), the oldest brachyceran thus would still be *Protobrachyceron liassinum* HANDLIRSCH, 1920 of the Lower Jurassic. This is known only from a wing of rather generalised rhagionid type; despite its antiquity, it already had an apomorphy in lacking the m-cu crossvein through CuA_1 being confluent with the discal cell. *Protobrachyceron* was attributed by some authors (HENNIG 1967, KOVALEV 1987) to Vermileonidae, but evidence for this is wholly inadequate. By the Middle Jurassic, a diversity of Rhagionidae, and some Archisolvidae, Mythicomyiidae and Rhagionempididae, existed. MOSTOVSKI (1998) summarised early brachyceran evolution

Figs 17-18: Heads of female Athericidae, showing ventral postpedicel enlargement in a haematophagous species (Fig. 17: *Suragina* spec. indet., Malawi) and postpedicel reduction in an autogenous species (Fig. 18: *Xerithia plaumanni* STUCKENBERG, Brazil). The enlargement provides more surface area for an expanded field of anteriorly-directed chemoreceptors.

Fig. 19: Generalised representation of a cyclorrhaphous antenna, showing terminology and hypothesized segmentation.

as follows: “The palaeontological record begins in the Early-Middle Triassic. In the Early Jurassic, not later than the Sinemurian [200 my] flies diverged into the Stratiomyomorpha and Asilomorpha ... The Rhagionidae are dominant in Jurassic oryctocoenoses.”

These Jurassic Rhagionidae commonly have the plesiomorphic form of antenna (Fig. 1). This raises the question: what could have prompted the evolution of this antenna, presumably from a flagelliform precursor in Triassic Nematocera? Its evolutionary origin may be linked to another feature of the Brachycera: the presence of pseudotracheae in the labella. The possibility that pseudotracheae are a synapomorphy of the Brachycera was discussed by HENNIG (1973); he was uncertain about it because of scattered reports of occurrences of pseudotracheae in some Nematocera, a matter he considered to require more research. Unfortunately, the literature on Nematocera is obscure about the prevalence of these structures. A survey of the family chapters in the ‘Manual of Nearctic Diptera’ (MCALPINE et al. 1981), for example, reveals hardly any mention of them, apart from a single pseudotrachea in each labellum in some Scatopsidae and Synneuridae; authors fail to state whether pseudotracheae are **absent**. Nevertheless, it is evident that these structures are sporadic and unusual in Nematocera. There is an old record of two Tipulidae with pseudotracheae (KELLOGG 1899), but their arrangement is different in these species. ZAITZEV (1984) illustrated pseudotracheae in a tipulid, and recorded them in unspecified Bibionidae. In Blephariceridae, it has recently become apparent that pseudotrachea-like structures are a synapomorphy of some genera of Apistomyiini (ZWICK 1998), but this is unique in the family. The long, slender labella that characterise this tribe have become adapted in these genera for flower-feeding by internal modification of each entire labellum into a single long pseudotrachea.

ZAITZEV (1984) arranged pseudotracheal forms selected from several families into a possible evolutionary series. He stated: “The form of pseudotrachea that we have found in the Tipulidae, Bibionidae, Rhagionidae, some Nemestrinidae, and some genera of Bombyliidae ... should apparently be considered closest to the original [the most plesiomorphic form].” Such scattered occurrences of a basic form indicate the possibility of considerable homoplasy, both between and within families. From their study of labellar modifications of Muscomorpha,

ELZINGA & BROCE (1986) concluded that in the 35 families sampled, "... the pseudotracheae are poor indicators of phylogeny," and, "... there was often more variation within families than between families." There is no evidence that development of pseudotracheae in Nematocera can be linked phylogenetically to their development in Brachycera. It seems certain that pseudotracheae are not part of the groundplan of any nematoceros family; they are part of the groundplan of all families of the Brachycera, even though within individual families they may be variably formed relative to feeding modes and food preferences, and may be secondarily lost in certain taxa with autogenous, predatory or non-feeding adult lifestyles.

Pseudotracheae have not yet been reported as preserved in compression fossils, but a typically brachycerous proboscis with large labella has been figured for several Middle Jurassic rhagionid taxa, such as species of *Palaeobrachyceron* KOVALEV, 1981 and *Palaeobolbomyia* KOVALEV, 1982. Especially clear illustrations are given of the relatively massive proboscis of the Upper Jurassic/Early Cretaceous *Palaeoarthroteles mesozoicus* KOVALEV & MOSTOVSKI, 1997; its labella were stout and its large palpi were curved over the apical segment (this may have been an early blood-sucking brachyceran). It is reasonable to assume that pseudotracheae were present in all such genera.

The simultaneous appearance in Jurassic rhagionids of the brachycerous antennal modifications and enlarged labella suggests that the origin of the Brachycera lay in the emergence of a new feeding mode, for which mouthpart and antennal structures were coadapted. It can be surmised that this feeding mode was associated with diversifying food resources that became available in the Triassic and Jurassic floras. Adaptive interactions between insects and plants are accepted by many authors as having had significant evolutionary consequences. This aspect of insect palaeobiology now has a substantial literature, reviewed by SCOTT et al. (1992) and LABANDEIRA (1997).

WHITE (1986) summarised land-plant evolution during this important period as follows: "There was a warm and wet interval at the end of the Permian and the beginning of the Triassic. These times saw the sudden appearance of a new flora characterised by the first forked-frond Seed-ferns, Podocarp conifers, Ferns, Ginkgos and Cycadophytes. The Glossopterids disappeared from the Fossil record." And: "The Jurassic Period was uniformly warm to hot, and wet world-wide, and there was a luxuriant cosmopolitan flora of Conifers, Cycads, Ferns, Seed-ferns, Ginkgos, and herbaceous Lycopods and Horsetails. The flora, which continues into the Early Cretaceous, is the last to be composed of plants from the ancient groups only. After the Jurassic, the changeover to modern-aspect flora commenced."

LABANDEIRA (1997) made a comprehensive categorisation of insect mouthparts in relation to feeding modes and their time of appearance in the fossil record. He found that during the Late Triassic and Early Jurassic, "... there was an explosion in mouthpart innovation and feeding strategies, with approximately one third of all modern mouthpart classes coming into existence." These innovations included a "dramatic increase" in fluid-feeding and particle-capturing mouthpart classes associated with the radiation of the Holometabola, particularly Diptera, and further expansion of surface-feeding strategies during the Late Jurassic and Early Cretaceous. He postulated that the presence of new food resources was probably attributable to the emergence of several seed plant clades during the Triassic, leading to increased interaction with insects. This included fluid-feeding by Diptera capable of surface sponging with pseudotracheate labella. LABANDEIRA also considered that such a feeding mode gave access to honeydew produced by the diversifying hemipteroid insects, whose haustellate-stylate feeding mode, directed at "nutritionally rewarding" plant sap, had already appeared in the Early

Permian. And, he conjectured that protein- and lipid-rich fluid exudates from carrion and exposed wounds of animals also became available to such Diptera.

The lapping and sponging mode of feeding with enlarged, pseudotracheate labella, allowing the external application of salivary enzymes, would have facilitated exploitation of those abundant resources. For the first time, adult Diptera were morphologically well adapted to obtain nutriment of plant origin. A walking, probing lifestyle would have been appropriate, involving constant physical and chemoreceptor exploration in the profusion of increasingly complex organs of the plants, with their abundance of spores, pollens, seeds and fruits, often in elaborate male and female cones, sporangiophores, and catkin-like structures – also on leaves in multitudinous forms and arrays, with their varied tissues, glandular secretions, surface irregularities, and surface-dwelling micro-organisms. There would have been a rich harvest for flies with such adaptations in the decomposition products of those plants, and doubtless in the copious dung produced by the herbivorous dinosaurs and their predators. Access to such nutritious diets would have promoted longer adult life, and, hence, possibly the advantage of repeated ovarian cycles.

This lifestyle probably favoured Diptera having compact bodies, broader wings, short legs, and more compact antennae with new specialisations for mechanoreception and enhanced olfactory chemoreception. The Jurassic rhagionids evidently were such flies. Perhaps the combination of flagellar differentiation with pseudotracheate labella was the first unequivocally brachycerous condition to evolve in the nematocerous ancestors. This combination (and with it the two-segmented condition of the maxillary palpus) would be the surest evidence of brachycerous affinities in a fossil – more conclusive than wing venation probably could be.

Pseudotracheate labella also made possible a further new feeding mode, involving elongation of the labium for insertion into recessed sources of plant sugars. This was an early development; by the Upper Jurassic, rostrate Nemestrinidae and flies assigned to the Tabanidae had appeared (REN 1998a, 1998b). The stage was set for rapid evolutionary response to new dietary opportunities offered in floral banquets by the radiating Angiosperms.

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